

**METHODOLOGY FOR INTERNATIONAL COMPARISON OF
MHT INDICATORS**

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ABSTRACT. This article focuses on the use of official exchange rates for the transfer of national currencies, real purchasing power parity (PPP), its coefficient characterizing the prices of goods in the countries of the world as a statistical category, the division of the volumes and flows of goods and services into changes over time, the many flows reflected in the PPS, deflation based on a price index, comparison of international indices of material volumes and measuring the purchasing power parity of different currencies from price comparisons.

Keywords: Official exchange rates, purchasing power parity (PPP), prices of goods, coefficient, transfers, quantitative parameter, deflation, intertemporal comparison, time series, PPS, “nominal volumes”, Paasche and Laspeyres indices, aggregation, etc.

INTRODUCTION

In solving this issue, priority is given to calculating real purchasing power parity (PPP) rather than using official exchange rates for the transfer of national currencies.

The GDP is a statistical category that reflects the ratio of prices of goods of the same quality in different countries of the world. Changes in the volume and flow of goods and services over time can be directly divided into two components. They reflect changes in the prices of goods and services and their physical volumes, respectively. Similarly, changes in the value of many types of asset

stocks can usually be divided into corresponding price components and physical volumes. However, many flows reflected in the GDP, for example, transfers in the form of money, do not have their own prices and quantitative parameters, so it is not possible to divide them into corresponding components. Such flows cannot be measured in constant prices, but they can be reflected in real terms. For this, their value is deflated based on a price index. This makes it possible to measure their real purchasing power in relation to a specially selected basket of goods and services that serves as a standard benchmark.

The same methodology used for comparing prices and volumes over time within a country can be used to compare them between countries. International indices of material volumes are useful for comparing productivity or living standards in different countries, while price comparisons can be used to measure the purchasing power parity of different currencies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Yu.N. Ivanova and others, international comparisons of macroeconomic indicators require the solution of two main problems. The first is the problem of unification of the economic content of the indicators being compared. The second problem is the problem of choosing a method for recalculating indicators in national currency into a single monetary unit.

The first problem can be solved by using standard international classifications and applying a single calculation methodology. The solution of the second problem (the choice of calculation formulas, measurements, methods of aggregation of private indices, etc.) is determined by the content, goals and objectives of the comparison being carried out, the initial data (its level of detail, accuracy, comparability), and the analytical requirements for the results[5].

According to V. Podmogilnaya, "In international comparisons, this is of greater importance than in intertemporal comparisons. No country in a group of

countries has such a natural status in the base period or as the first in a time series. Usually, there are no well-founded economic reasons for singling out one country as a base country. In addition, the choice of a base country in international comparisons has a significant impact on the final results, since the structure and volume of relative prices in countries can differ significantly from each other in relation to prices in the same and successive periods in the same country”[6].

According to B.K. Goyibnazarov, “To evaluate sample goods, average prices characteristic of the economy are generally used. This allows us to achieve consistency between the calculated price indices and GDP estimates using the methods adopted by the MNT. In cases where the same product is sold to the population at different prices through different distribution channels, the average price of the goods sold through different channels, estimated by the volume of goods, is calculated. In the specialized literature, this method is called the “potato-is-a-potato” principle. The use of such a principle means that when calculating indices characterizing the ratio between the prices of two countries for a particular product, differences in the level of trade and transport surcharges of different countries are not taken into account”[9]. According to A. Abdugoforov et al., comparisons are a way to calculate the average of the GDP for various aggregated categories and GDP. International ratios of material volumes for the first groups and aggregated categories are calculated in the same way. Regardless of the formula used in the aggregation process, the arithmetic complexity of the work increases with the amount of primary data that must be evaluated at the same time. However, the computational and logical complexity of the international comparison procedure is even more complicated: they argue that most of the errors are associated with violations in the requirements for individual goods a obtained for their own country and their own group and in the requirements for the comparability of the goods groups of their partners in comparisons - countries [7].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research used a wide range of methods such as logical thinking, reasoning, observation, comparison, selection, generalization, dynamic change detection, macroeconomic data analysis, induction and deduction, classification, algorithmization, programming, comparative comparison and expert assessment.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

It should be noted that the theory of indices developed for time series cannot be mechanically transferred to international comparisons. There are a number of specific features that distinguish international comparisons. The specific features of international comparisons are primarily related to the following:

1. In time series, it is customary to compare two periods that can be compared in time (for example, one year). In international comparisons, countries or regions that are the same are usually not compared. However, countries with different levels of economic development can be compared with each other. In this case, the analysis of the results obtained in this way becomes significantly complicated, and sometimes the question of the appropriateness of conducting such comparisons arises.

2. Sometimes, depending on the goals and objectives of the comparisons being made, it becomes necessary to modify the statistical units under consideration. For example, it is possible to highlight some similar districts in countries or to enlarge the objects of research in international organizations. These features are also very important when conducting international comparisons. It is necessary to calculate price indicators and material volumes not only for blocks of countries, but also for individual countries. In this regard, the significance of the level of development of countries should not depend on whether the country is considered as a group of regions, as a separate independent unit, or as part of a larger international organization.

3. In time series, the continuity between the registration of prices and volumes and the changes in prices and material volumes over time in successive time periods is preserved. There are no such clearly consecutive series between countries. Accordingly, there is no universal method for objectively organizing countries and then forming chained (dynamic) indices for them. Therefore, chained indices are used much less often than such methods for comparisons of prices and production volumes and their consumption over time in cross-country comparisons.

Comparisons are made not only for pairs of countries, but also for groups of countries, regions, districts. In this regard, pairwise and multilateral comparisons are distinguished.

The UN International Comparisons Program can be considered as a logical development of the MST in the transition from data at current and variable prices to an intercountry set of international accounts in national currencies.

The PPP shows the amount of currency units of country A (the comparison country) needed to purchase a standard set of goods and services that can be purchased with one currency unit of country B (or any other country taken as a basis of comparison) or with one conditional (common) currency unit of a group of countries.

The value of national currencies calculated in relation to the currency that can be compared using the PPP is called “real volumes”. At the same time, the value of national currencies calculated in relation to the currency that is compared at exchange rates for international comparisons is called “nominal volumes”. The PPP is a kind of spatial “deflator”, an analogue of the price dynamics index. If the price dynamics index measures the change in the purchasing power of a country’s currency over time, then the PPP measures the differences in the purchasing power of currencies of different countries in space.

In practice, the PPI indices are mainly used to form international indices of material volumes. They are mainly used to deflate the ratio between values in national currencies. In addition, they are of considerable interest in themselves. These indices have parameters similar to exchange rates and can be directly compared with the latter. By dividing the PPI index by the corresponding exchange rate, it is possible to obtain a price index similar to the intertemporal price index. Such an index shows how much higher (or lower) the prices of goods and services in country "B" are on average compared to the prices of goods and services in the same country "A" when recalculated into the currency of country "A" at the current exchange rate. Such information is useful for individuals or institutional units moving from one country to another or engaged in economic activity in these two countries. Since the PPI, as a rule, refers to final domestic expenditures, they are not intended for the analysis of international flows of goods and services, but they can be of significant interest when analyzing foreign trade.

To ensure the logical and analytical possibility of aggregating data on various goods and groups of goods, the results of comparisons (including PPI), which are usually obtained in the form of indices, must meet a number of analytical descriptive requirements:

1. Specificity means that the measurement systems used to calculate PPI must sufficiently reflect the specific characteristics of the structure of indicators and the price structure of all countries under study: often, descriptiveness is understood as the independence of the results of indicators of two countries from data from third countries.

2. Invariance means that the results of the calculation of the CPI should not depend on the chosen comparison base (base country, base measurements, etc.). If the invariance requirements are not met, the comparison results will in most cases be determined by the measurement systems, etc., which will lead to some distortion of the results obtained.

3. Transitivity (an analogue of the circularity requirement in dynamic comparisons) means that direct pairwise comparisons of the CPI should give the same results as indirect comparisons obtained through a third “bridge” country (bridge country method). In a strictly formal formulation of the problem, a set of indices (CPI) is considered transitive if the following conditions are met for each triad of indices:

$$I_{(A/B)} = I_{(A/C)} : I_{(C/B)} \quad (1)$$

If the CPI does not meet the transitivity requirements, this can lead to logical inconsistencies. For example, the indicator of country “A” calculated using the CPI is higher than the indicator of country “V”, the indicator of country “V” is higher than the indicator of country “C”, but the indicator of country “C” is higher than the indicator of country “A”: $A > B$, $B > C$; but $C > A$.

The index calculated by the direct method is considered a chain index in terms of statistical structure, which connects countries “A” and “V”, where country “C” is used as the connecting country.

4. Additivity means that the CPI should be calculated for the overall indicator and for its components in such a way that the calculations of the overall results for the indicator should consist of the results of the calculations of its components. This requirement is often referred to in the literature as the requirement of internal consistency. If the additivity requirement is not met, then this situation can lead to internal logical inconsistencies. For example, in the currency being compared, all components of the indicator of country “A” are greater than the components of the indicator of country “B”, but the total indicator of country “B” is greater than the total indicator of country “A”.

5. The factorial model requirement means that the product of the price index (i.e., the PPI) and the volume index of material goods must be exactly equal to the value index.

The above-mentioned formal requirements are in a certain logical contradiction with each other. For example, transitivity and descriptiveness: let's say, to satisfy the first requirement, uniform measurements should be used, while to satisfy the second requirement, ideally, each pair of countries should use their own units of measurement. Therefore, in any multilateral comparison, only a certain amount of compromise can be achieved between the fulfillment of these requirements.

Similar types of indices are used to calculate the CPI between the currencies of two countries, as are used to compare prices dynamically.

At the level of primary commodity groups, the unweighted geometric mean formula of the index is used for individual price ratios:

$$I_{ggr}(A/B) = (Ii_j(A/B))^{1/m} \quad (2)$$

Here: $i_j(A/B)$ – Price index for individual goods of "country "A" relative to country "B";

$I_{ggr}(A/B)$ – The group geometric mean of the price index "Country "A" relative to Country "B" (for primary commodity groups);

m – number of samples in the group.

This approach is based on one of the methods of international multilateral comparisons - the Girardi method. When using the Girardi method, average international prices are calculated based on average national prices determined using the unweighted geometric mean formula. The indices obtained on this basis meet the requirements of transitivity, additivity and independence from the

selected base country. When using the Girardi formula, the Gershen effect does not affect the comparison results. However, the economic content of average international prices calculated using the Girardi formula is abstract. Nevertheless, the Girardi formula has been used for some time in international comparisons of GDP based on the GDP of European countries by Eurostat.

The use of the unweighted index formula is explained by the lack of internationally comparable and reliable data on the measurements of individual representatives, and the choice of the geometric index formula is explained by formal-analytical considerations (the geometric index ensures invariance, i.e., the reversibility of the indices).

The aggregated level of the GDP can be obtained using the aggregate of the Paasche and Laspeyres indices, using the GDP calculated according to the above-mentioned group average formula, and the measurements of commodity groups in national currency.

If we:

P_a, q_a, P_b, q_b – The quantities and prices of certain goods in countries "A" and "B";

Q_a, Q_b – The value volumes of the group of goods in the national currencies of countries "A" and "B";

$i_p = P_b / P_a$ – We may have a certain opportunity if we have a price index of the j-sample-good in country "B" relative to country "A".

According to the Paasche and Laspeyres formula, the CPI takes the form of a simple average of indices, and a harmonized and arithmetically approximated form for commodity groups, respectively:

$$XKП_{Пааше} = (\Sigma Q_b) / \Sigma(Q_b / i_p) \quad XKП_{Ласнейрес} = (\Sigma i_p Q_a) / \Sigma Q_a \quad (3)$$

According to the Paasche formula, the GDP corresponds to the corresponding Laspeyres material volume index and is inversely proportional. Usually, there is a significant difference between the Paasche index and the Laspeyres values. This is explained by the fact that relative prices and quantities between countries tend to be inversely correlated - a phenomenon also known as the Gerschenkron effect: institutional units in a country tend to purchase relatively more goods and services that are relatively cheaper in that country than in other countries. Given the significant differences between the Paasche and Laspeyres indices, the Fisher index is usually used as the official result in international bilateral and interbank comparisons. It is the geometric mean of the two indices:

$$I = \sqrt{XKП_{Пааше} * XKП_{Ласнейрес}} \quad (4)$$

The Fisher index ensures the invariance of results in bilateral comparisons, which explains its widespread use in international comparisons. In addition, the Fisher index is one of the methods for calculating the results of multilateral comparisons, a special case of the more complex methods of calculating the GDP. For example, the Van Izeren method, the Giri-Kamish method, the EKSh method, the Walsh method, and other methods also deserve a more detailed consideration.

The Giri-Kamish method has been used for a long time to carry out multilateral international comparisons of GDP. The Giri-Kamish index formula looks like this:

$$\bar{p}_i = \frac{\sum_j^m P_{ij} q_{ij} R_j}{Q_i}, i = 1, \dots, n; \quad (5)$$

$$R_j = \frac{\sum_i^n q_{ij} \bar{p}_i}{\sum_i^n p_{ij} q_{ij}}, j = 1, \dots, m;$$

(6)

Here: R_j – j - purchasing power parity of a country's currency against the currency of a base country; $\bar{p}_i$ – Average international price of an i -good; p_{ij} – j - price of the i -good in the country; q_{ij} – the quantity of the i -good in the j -country; Q_i – total quantity of the i -th good in all countries; n – quantity of goods; m – number of countries.

Thus, based on the system of solving linear equations using the Giri-Kamic method, a simultaneous XQP is obtained. (R_i) and average international prices ($\bar{p}_i$) is determined. Estimating the indicators of all countries at international prices also allows us to obtain indices that are transitive, additive and independent of the choice of the base country. However, the Giri-Kamic indices do not meet the requirements for descriptiveness of the measurements, which is their disadvantage. Therefore, the Giri-Kamic method was superseded by the EKSH (Elte-Kevesh-Schuls) method. In these two frameworks, the average prices obtained in the aggregation process are used (which the Giri-Kamic method uses directly, and the EKSH method uses indirectly), but the EKSH method prices, unlike the Giri-Kamic method prices, according to a number of reputable expert groups, are more neutral (neutral) with respect to the national price structure.

The EKSH aggregation method used in the 1990 and 1993 EKSH differs from the aggregation procedure used in all previous stages of the EKSH and EKSH. The formula for the EEC index for countries “A” and “B” is as follows:

$$\mathcal{E}KIII_{A/B} = \sqrt[n]{(F_{A/B})^2 \left(\frac{F_{A_j}}{F_{B_j}} \right)},$$

(7)

Here: $F_{A/B}$ – Fisher index for countries "A" and "B"; F_{A_j} – Fisher index for countries "A" and "J"; F_{B_j} – Fisher index for countries "V" and "J"; n – number of countries participating in the comparison; $j = A, B, C, \dots, j$.

Based on the EKSh formula, it is possible to obtain indices that meet the transitivity requirement and deviate minimally from the requirement of descriptiveness of measurements. It is worth noting that in the EKSh formula, the Fisher index has a scale equal to two for these pairs of countries ("A" and "V"). In addition, the Fisher indices obtained indirectly, that is, through the country-by-country method, for these two pairs of countries are also taken into account.

The Walsh method is also described in the relevant literature. Its formula looks like this:

$$\bar{I}_{A/B} = \prod_{i=1}^n R_{i_{A/B}}^{(M_i)},$$

(8)

Here: $R_{i_{A/B}}$ – Purchasing power parity of currencies for the i -th commodity group (calculated as the geometric mean of the ratio of prices for the sample goods of countries "A" and "B");

M_i – The weight of a group of general aggregates is determined as the average weight of this group of goods in all countries participating in the comparison of GDP. For example, if the weight of expenditure on meat products in countries "A", "B" and "C" is equal to 5, 6 and 7, then M for this group of goods is equal to 6.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-12

Walsh indices meet the requirements of the transitive and base country selection index, which is their advantage. However, they do not meet the requirement of additivity.

In some cases, the “central country solution” is used for multilateral comparisons. In this indicator, the GDP of all countries is compared with the GDP of the country selected as the base (central) country. In this case, for pairs of countries considered (except for pairs of countries where one of the two is not a central country), the indices are calculated directly by the direct method, that is, by comparing the index values of these countries with the values of the central country. The indices obtained by such a method are transitive, but their transitivity is achieved by a contrived method and they do not meet the requirement of non-separability depending on the choice of the central country. Therefore, the indices calculated by the direct method mentioned above $I_{B/C}$ The index is calculated based on the random pairwise comparison of countries “V” and “C” $I_{B/C}$ differs from the index. The central country method, which is widely used in the practice of such multilateral international comparisons, is not considered a primary objective. Its main advantage is the ease of calculation, however. In the most general form, if the national expenditure indicator is the corresponding GDP per unit of the specified primary groups, then we have a converted synthetic indicator of this value in another currency. This is a general concept for carrying out quantitative comparisons based on data on the ratio of expenditures and prices.

The above procedure is used in direct pairwise (bilateral) comparisons of GDP based on GDP, that is, in comparisons carried out directly for one or another pair of countries. In addition, the procedure and requirements of this procedure are relevant for the theory of international comparisons. Here, it is customary to distinguish between pairwise and multilateral comparisons, which are carried out simultaneously for entire groups of countries. International economic organizations (UN, OECD (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development), World

Bank, etc.) usually carry out multilateral comparisons. The peculiarity of multilateral comparisons is that they are carried out not only for a group of countries, but also in that information on the volume of products produced and consumed in these countries and their prices is processed as a single set of data necessary to obtain a system of interrelated indices that meet the above-mentioned analytical requirements.

The implementation of the step-by-step basic method begins with a complete matrix of group parities at the level of primary groups. For each subsequent year, some parities are replaced by new ones using prices accumulated during the year, and the rest are extrapolated using group price indices. The matrix is then aggregated to obtain the PPI and real volumes. The cycle continues until all initial parities are completely replaced, which takes about three years. The disadvantages of this method are the need to continuously collect data for a part of the representative list of goods, the need to constantly submit price indices at the level of primary groups, and the need to annually estimate detailed GDP expenditures. In this process, most OECD member countries have detailed indices, for example, for investment goods. Therefore, they all aggregate prices for a representative sample of goods, such as “Machinery and equipment”, which is a different aggregated goods group. This significantly reduces the quality of the extrapolation. The global extrapolation method can only indicate PPI and real volumes at the GDP level, since it is based on the ratios of GDP deflators.

$$XKII_{i+1} = XKII_i * (I_{\partial e\phi n}^{i+1}(K) / I_{\partial e\phi n}^{i+1}(Ba3)) \quad (9)$$

Here $I_{\partial e\phi n}^{i+1}(K)$ va $I_{\partial e\phi n}^{i+1}(Ba3)$ – deflator-indexes, respectively, the deflators of the “K” country and the base country (for example, the USA or Austria).

Thus, the global extrapolation method can be used on the basis of the GDP material volume index of the base country and other countries. The disadvantage of

global extrapolation methods is the use of material volume indices and GDP deflators calculated on different bases. As a result, errors occur in the estimates, which eliminates the possibility of extrapolating the results for the long term, extrapolating only between the comparison years.

Despite all the complexities and limitations of various international comparison programs, they can only provide socio-economic information that allows us to compare the living standards of the population in different countries with similar levels of cultural and economic development and to make assumptions about the price ratios for similar goods.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the analytical capabilities of the NMS, it is important to provide a methodological basis for calculating all stages of national accounts indicators (from obtaining primary data to compiling balance sheets). The political and economic nature of the Republic of Uzbekistan, based on the principles of the NMS, is aimed at a number of special requirements for internal economic structures.

The resulting indicators are considered comprehensively for each area of activity, industry, institutional sector, form of ownership, and business management system. Therefore, in order to study their activities in more depth, it is necessary to conduct targeted statistical observation, ensure a high level of statistical coverage, and fully comply with market principles in current statistical reports. This will ensure that the resulting indicators at the central levels fully reflect quality information, and also create an expanded opportunity to study, analyze, and evaluate the national economy based on international principles.

Macroeconomics uses many indicators aimed at various purposes (GDP, net domestic product, gross national income, etc.). The most important of them is the GDP indicator. GDP is widely used in international practice. It serves as an

indicator that reflects the final results of economic production activities in international and national practice. The general accounts of the MNE reflect various aspects of GDP reproduction: production, formation, distribution and accumulation, as well as a number of other purposes. In GDP, interconnected and mutually dependent goods and services, income flows are gradually reflected in the process of reproduction. Taking into account the above circumstances, this indicator has been calculated in Uzbekistan since 1992. They are mainly calculated at current and comparable prices. The calculation of GDP in the Republic of Uzbekistan is intended for international comparison with world countries and for fulfilling the requirements of the UN Statistical Commission.

The movement of GDP by stages of production should be shown in two aspects: value and consumption value. In the first case, GDP is interpreted as a flow of goods and services, and in the second case, as a flow of monetary income. These flows are separated as an integral part of the movement of GDP by stages of production. In the production method, GDP is determined by the sum of gross value added in economic sectors and institutional sectors and net taxes on products. Gross value added in economic sectors and institutional sectors is the difference between gross goods and services produced and intermediate consumption. The economy is divided into institutional sectors, the study of which serves to classify changes in financial assets and liabilities, income and expenses. Its results are compared with the results of economic sectors.

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